

ТЕОРІЯ ТА МЕТОДИКА НАВЧАННЯ

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Innovative Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages to Students of Non-linguistic Specialties

Yevheniia Makarska

Senior Lecturer of the Department of Business Foreign Language and Translation, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University,
61022, 4 Svobody Square, Kharkiv, Kharkiv Oblast, Ukraine,
kafmov2018@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3899-4488>

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***Abstract.** The article presents a comprehensive analysis of the innovative methods to teaching foreign languages to the students of non-linguistic specialties, focusing on the integration of professional orientation and language learning. It is argued that aligning students' individual interests, aptitudes, and career expectations with the educational process significantly enhances motivation and engagement. The author identifies professional interest and the recognition of the practical value of language skills as essential motivators for successful language acquisition.*

The article emphasizes the importance of active and student-centered learning strategies, including small group collaboration, discussions, case studies, project-based learning, and the implementation of information and communication technologies. These methods contribute to the development of cognitive activity, critical thinking, teamwork, and the ability to apply knowledge in professional contexts. Special attention is given to the benefits of small group work, which

promotes positive interdependence, equal participation, and the formation of social and communicative competencies.

Furthermore, the case method is examined as an effective means of modeling real-life professional scenarios, fostering analytical thinking and decision-making skills. Project-based learning is presented as a tool for stimulating intellectual curiosity and developing skills such as research, collaboration, self-evaluation, and public presentation.

In conclusion, the article underlines that modern foreign language education must go beyond linguistic training and support of the development of key and professional competencies, thus preparing students for effective participation in their future professional environments.

Keywords: *modern approach, basic teaching methods, future specialists, foreign language, non-linguistic specialties.*

Сучасні методи викладання іноземних мов для студентів немовних спеціальностей

Євгенія Макарьська

старший викладач кафедри ділової іноземної мови та перекладу
Харківського національного університету імені В.Н. Каразіна, 61022, майдан
Свободи, 4, Харків, Харківська область, Україна, kafmov2018@gmail.com,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3899-4488>

Анотація. *У статті розглянуто інноваційні підходи до організації навчання іноземної мови на немовних факультетах. Обґрунтовано доцільність інтеграції професійної спрямованості у процес вивчення іноземної мови з метою підвищення мотивації здобувачів освіти. Автор підкреслює, що одним із ключових чинників ефективного мовного навчання є професійна зацікавленість*

та усвідомлення практичної значущості іноземної компетентності у майбутній професійній діяльності.

Особливу увагу приділено активним методам навчання: роботі в малих групах, кейс-методу, проєктній діяльності, використанню інтерактивних технологій та інформаційно-комунікаційних засобів. Окреслено педагогічні умови, що сприяють формуванню пізнавальної активності, критичного мислення, комунікативних умінь та здатності працювати в команді. Акцентовано на ефективності групових форм навчання, які забезпечують соціальну взаємодію, позитивну міжособистісну залежність і відповідальність кожного учасника освітнього процесу.

Розкрито потенціал кейс-методу у формуванні аналітичного мислення та навичок прийняття рішень. Описано можливості проєктної методики як засобу розвитку творчого потенціалу, дослідницьких умінь і навичок самоорганізації. Зазначено, що впровадження зазначених підходів сприяє формуванню не лише іноземної, але й ключових та професійних компетентностей, необхідних для успішної професійної самореалізації майбутніх фахівців.

Ключові слова: сучасний підхід, основні методи навчання, майбутні фахівці, іноземна мова, немовні спеціальності.

Problem statement. In the era of emerging educational technologies, more effective and efficient methods for teaching foreign languages are being developed, as international integration has become a top priority. Foreign language learning is now an essential component of professional training for future specialists, as proficiency in a foreign language enhances their competitiveness and mobility in the global job market and supports career advancement. The growing emphasis on international academic mobility further underscores the practical importance of foreign language proficiency in higher education institutions, providing students with

opportunities to acquire up-to-date knowledge and gain practical experience abroad. Moreover, students to higher education institutions who intend to undertake internships or practical training abroad are required to meet additional foreign language proficiency standards.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. The problem of foreign language teaching to the students of non-linguistic specialties was studied by T.P.Holub [5], Yu.V. Pavlovska [7], Yu. Degtyareva, T. Karaeva, T. Korzh, Z. Korneva, O. Penkova, etc. Researches emphasize the importance of integrating the latest educational technologies into the process of teaching foreign languages. Some scholars addressing this issue have employed educational projects and game-based learning methods (J. Richards, T.Rogers [1], C.Herreid [2], N.Anrushchenko [3], O.Bezkorovaina, O.Dyshchakovska [4] , N.Volkova [12], A.Kuzmichov [13], etc.), believing that such means of teaching a foreign language will allow combining educational and cognitive activities with a real professional environment. The use of the latest multimedia technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language was studied by A.Tenant [14], T.Slater, G.Beckett [15], I.Montse [16], T.Koval [18], R. Zapotichna, O.Romanyuk [20], etc. Scientists propose to use different approaches to teaching speaking, reading, listening and writing to the students of higher educational institutions. However, despite the variety of methodological studies, the problem of choosing approaches to teaching a foreign language for non-linguistic specialties remains relevant and in demand.

Identification of previously unsolved parts of the overall problem. The analysis of the preparedness of students in educational institutions of Ukraine shows that the use of traditional forms and methods of teaching does not guarantee a satisfactory level of proficiency in foreign languages. Thus, it is necessary to look for more innovative approaches to language learning. Despite numerous studies on the presented issues, there are enough aspects for further exploration, namely: comparing certain approaches to learning foreign languages, their advantages and disadvantages,

the suitability of approaches to learners, available resources and various learning situations.

Formulating the goals of the article (task statement). The objective of the article is to analyze the innovative methods of teaching foreign languages to the students of non-linguistic specialties.

Presentation of the primary research material. Since one of the key conditions for effectively training future specialists is aligning their interests, aptitudes and abilities with their chosen profession, the study of a foreign language should be approached through the lens of students' attitudes toward their careers. The strongest motivating factor is professional interest, along with understanding of the theoretical and practical significance of foreign language proficiency for their future professional activities.

In order to purposefully develop the activity and interest of future specialists in the process of teaching a foreign language, one should use the most effective methods of organizing educational activities; create conditions not only for the development of educational interest, but also the creative activity of students. The task of a lecturer is to create conditions for the practical mastering a foreign language, development of positive motivation; choose such forms, methods and teaching aids that would allow each student to intensify their cognitive activity. According to the author, the use of interactive learning formats – such as small group work, discussions, and training sessions – combined with diverse teaching methods, including project-based learning, student portfolio creation, and role-playing or business games, as well as the integration of information and communication technologies, such as multimedia presentations and Internet-based resources, significantly enhances the effectiveness of foreign language teaching [11, p.104], work in small groups promotes activation of cognitive activity of students and formation of steady positive motivation.

The method of uniting students into microgroups for joint performance of the task is one of the most popular technologies of higher education institutions. The

technology of teaching in small groups is based on the following principles: social interaction of students, positive interdependence, personal responsibility of each group member, equal share of each student's participation. A key feature of this method is the active involvement of all students in the group. It fosters teamwork skills and encourages a positive attitude towards the opponent with different views. Each student has the opportunity to express their own opinion, and a significant amount of new material can be learned in a short time. Additionally, it helps develop skills in tolerant communication, the ability to justify one's point of view, and explore alternative solutions to the problems.

In the process of teaching a foreign language, a wide range of methods and techniques can be effectively employed within small group settings. The variety of exercise types and activities compatible with the communicative approach is virtually limitless, as long as they support the communicative goals of the curriculum. These activities should actively engage learners in communication and foster the use of communicative processes such as information exchange, negotiation of meaning, and interaction. Classroom tasks are often structured around meaningful goals that are mediated through language and involve collaborative negotiation and sharing of information [1, p.76]. Thus, when discussing the problem, it is advisable to use a "brainstorming", which involves the spontaneous expression of ideas, facts about the proposed topic or situation. However, the success of teamwork in small groups largely depends on the students' psychological readiness for collaboration and their willingness to work together. Equally important are the personal and professional qualities of the lecturer, including the ability to effectively organize group activities, prepare appropriate materials, and structure the process. Small group work should be applied to the tasks that involve complex problems requiring collective discussion and cooperative, rather than individual, efforts.

The case study method is a highly flexible instructional approach that incorporates problem-based learning and fosters the development of students'

analytical skills [2, p. 76]. The case study method is grounded in the description of specific professional activities, modeling real-world professional process in conditions that align with the training content. Students analyze a specific case that describes real events (situations). The content of cases can be a variety of professional texts, articles from newspapers and magazines, videos and audio, etc. After getting acquainted with the case, students discuss it in small groups. This method is characterized by collective cognitive activity, incorporating various techniques such as brainstorming and idea exchange, discussion, interpersonal interaction, which leads to active communication. Learning in cooperation, collective methods of educational work provide easy cognitive activity and a high level of educational communication of students. The use of the approach to analyzing specific situations in the process of foreign language teaching, according to the researchers, contributes to the solution of the following educational goals: development of analytical thinking, the use of analysis in dynamics; mastering practical skills of working with information (isolation, structuring and ranking according to importance of problems); making management decisions; development of the ability to select optimal strategies for effective interpersonal interaction [3, p.7].

In accordance with modern requirements, in addition to professional competencies, future specialists need to form general competencies, including the ability to analyze and synthesize, search, process and analyze information from various sources; ability to apply knowledge in practical situations. In the training case, future specialists acquire the following professional skills: they learn to distribute tasks, establish communication (cooperate), make informed decisions; take joint responsibility for their implementation and the final result. Solving situational tasks, students gain their own experience necessary for future professional activity.

The technology of teaching English using the project method is based on involving students in active cognitive activities. Researchers define the project

method as a learning system aimed not only at acquiring basic knowledge, skills and abilities, but also at developing creative abilities and forming intellectual abilities in the process of solving problem situations.

Certain requirements must be considered when applying the project-based methodology in foreign language teaching. Most importantly, the project should address a problem of scientific or research significance that necessitates the integration of knowledge from various domains. Lessons should foster a creative atmosphere in which all students actively participate in the cognitive process. In this context, the focus shifts from purely linguistic aspects to the content of the task, motivating students to work independently in search of solutions using diverse sources such as manuals, reference books, dictionaries, and online resources. Through project work, students can unlock their creative potential while developing a wide range of skills, including research, social interaction, evaluation (both of process and outcomes), presentation (public speaking, responding to questions, and using visual aids), and reflection (the ability to adopt an observer's perspective and assess others' contribution). Additionally, project implementation often involves teamwork, which promotes mutual respect, collaboration, and effective planning. The success of a project team relies on the coordinated efforts of all its members and their ability to share responsibilities effectively [8, p.75]. Thus, the application of the project method involves gaining experience in search activities, processing significant amounts of information, its analysis, systematization and further presentation; broadening horizons; development of creative potential; ensures the formation of key and professional competencies of future specialists.

The potential contribution of this article lies in the introduction of the innovative, student-oriented methods of teaching foreign languages to students of non-linguistic specialities by integrating professional orientation into the educational process. The article emphasizes the importance of combining language training with development of the key and professional competencies of future specialists, which

allows to increase motivation, student engagement and the effectiveness of preparation for a real professional environment.

Conclusions. The modern requirements for foreign language preparing of future professionals in higher education institutions requires the implementation of the innovative methods in language teaching strategies. Accordingly, creative strategies for foreign languages teaching aim to foster the personal and professional development of individuals, unlock their latent capacities and constructive potential, and create conditions for the effective enhancement of the educational process. Applying active learning strategies encourages deeper cognitive participation from students and improves their professional competencies, such as being able to analyze, work collaboratively, and defend their own viewpoints.

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